

Classification of Return on Equity (ROE) using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract

Return on Equity (ROE) is one of the most closely monitored financial ratios by shareholders and potential investors. A negative ROE can send an unfavourable message to investors and deter them from investing. This study identifies the financial ratios that influence ROE and determines the best machine learning techniques (out of Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB), and Random Forest (RF)) for predicting ROE, using a binary form of ROE, to avoid vigorous model assumptions.

The imbalanced dataset, sourced from the Integrated Real-time Equity System (IRESS), consisted of all companies listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange in 2019. The dataset was balanced using original observations from previous years (dataset 2) and the SMOTE and ROSE oversampling methods. Additionally, we assessed the performance of three shrinkage methods—Lasso, Elastic Net, and Ridge Regression—specifically in terms of feature selection. The model evaluation metrics used included sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy.

The best predictors of ROE identified by the classifiers were net profit margin, interest cover, earnings per share, earnings yield, and price-to-earnings ratio. The Random Forest method emerged as the most effective feature selection technique, consistently identifying similar predictors across all datasets. It also effectively validated the selected features, even with imbalanced data. When the SMOTE dataset was utilized, the model achieved sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy values of 99.2%, 99.6%, 99.6%, 99.4%, and 99.5%, respectively. The ROSE dataset yielded scores of 100%, 98.8%, 98.6%, 99.3%, and 99.3%. Dataset 2 yielded scores of 99.3%, 98.6%, 98.6%, 98.9%, and 98.9%, respectively.

The study encourages investors to prioritize companies with low price-to-earnings ratios, high net profit margins, high interest cover, high earnings per share, and high earnings yield when making investment decisions, using the Random Forest method.

Key Words: Classification, K-Nearest Neighbour, Logistic Regression, Machine Learning, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, Return on Equity, Stock Exchange.

1. Introduction

Every investor needs accurate information before investing in the capital market. Incorrect information can mislead investors in making sound investment decisions and result in losses for them (Pinuji, 2009; Rosikah, Prananingrum, Muthalib, Azis & Rohansyah, 2018). The Stock Exchange provides fair and transparent pricing for listed companies to limit the risk of share trading and has strict regulations that all listed companies must comply with (Muchabaiwa, 2013). The largest stock exchange in Africa is the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE), also known as the Johannesburg Securities Exchange (De Beer, Keyser & van der Merwe 2015). The main aim of every investor is to maximize profit and minimize loss; hence, investing in the most successful or promising company is essential. This means comparing different companies using the right tools is very important before investing.

The best way to compare different companies in the financial market is through financial ratios (AngelOne, 2022). It is also the most popular and widely used financial analysis tool (Hery 2015:20,

Aniyah, Supriyanto, Kumoro, Novitasari, Yuwono & Asbari 2020). Profitability ratios, the most widely used financial ratios, are primarily used to determine whether a company will succeed or fail. Return on Equity (ROE) is a financial ratio used by investors to check whether their investments are profitable (Josue, 2015). From an investor's perspective, a higher ROE indicates a higher rate of return on investment (Saragih, 2018). ROE is calculated as (Net income after tax)/(Total Equity) x 100.

Many studies have been conducted in the past to identify financial ratios that influence ROE, but all use a continuous dependent variable. Various methods, such as the DuPont formula, Correlation analysis, and multiple linear regression (MLR), have been used to identify determinants of ROE. However, all those methods are limited in one way or another. Both the DuPont formula and correlation analysis are limited in that they cannot be used to find a collective influence of ROE, nor can they be used to predict ROE. The limitation of MLR is its stringent assumptions, which are often not met, leading to biased and inconsistent results (Kharatyan, 2016).

ROE can be positive or negative. According to Fernando (2023), negative ROE communicates a loss to shareholders. Petryni (2022) stated that a positive ROE indicates shareholders are gaining, while a negative ROE indicates shareholders are incurring losses on their investment. For binary purposes, ROE was coded as follows.

$$ROE = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{to represent a positive Return on Equity} \\ 0 & \text{to represent a negative Return on Equity} \end{cases}$$

This study aims to fit a Logistic regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), K Nearest Neighbour (KNN), and Naive Bayes (NB) to the data using the binary dependent variable ROE, to find the determinants of ROE, and identify the best Machine Learning (ML) technique that can predict ROE. This will help investors identify companies likely to deliver better returns on their investments. It will also provide answers as to which Machine learning technique can be used to predict ROE for companies listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange and other Stock Exchanges.

2. Literature Review

Many researchers have studied financial ratios in the capital market that may yield dividends to an investor. Also, there have been many studies on identifying the best Machine learning (ML) to adopt across many fields of endeavor.

2.1 Return on Equity

Nasution et al. (2019) investigated the impact of total asset turnover and DTE ratio on ROE for listed companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange. The companies selected were from the automotive industry, and their components were sampled with a sample size of 50. Ten companies were selected. The statistical technique used to analyze the data was multiple linear regression. They concluded that the Debt-to-Equity ratio negatively affects ROE, while Total Asset Turnover positively affects ROE. It was also found that DTE and Total Asset Turnover combined do affect ROE.

Aniyah et al. (2020) conducted a study to examine the influence of the Quick ratio (QR), DTE ratio, and Total Asset Turnover on ROE for companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2012 to 2019. The test of the classical assumption was conducted in SPSS version 25. The relationship between ROE and the Quick ratio was found to be positive but insignificant. ROE and Total Asset Turnover also showed a positive, but insignificant, relationship. It was the Debt-to-Equity ratio that had a negative but insignificant relationship. The three independent variables, taken together, showed a negative association with ROE, but the effect was not significant.

Gharaibeh and Khaled (2020) conducted a study to examine the impact of capital structure and financial characteristics on profitability among Jordanian service-sector companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. The independent variables used were capital structure, consisting of Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Assets (DTA). The financial characteristics consisted of business risk,

growth, size, and tangible assets. Their findings were that size and growth positively impact profitability, namely, EBIT/TA and ROE.

Kim, Duvernay, and Thanh (2021) used Oaxaca decomposition and regression analysis to examine the diversity of financial performance among listed food product manufacturers in Vietnam for the period 2014 to 2019. The independent variables used were Quick ratios, total assets turnover ratios, leverage ratios, company size, sales growth, and CPI. They concluded that growth in sales and total assets turnover does impact ROE and Return on sales. It was also discovered that leverage ratios negatively impact Return on sales.

Tekin (2022) used panel data regression analysis to identify financial indicators that statistically influence ROA and ROE in the energy sector in Turkey. The companies targeted were gas, oil, electricity, and renewable energy producers and distributors in Turkey that are listed on the Borsa Istanbul Stock Exchange. The period targeted was 2010, Quarter 1, to 2019, Quarter 4. The two dependent variables used were ROE and ROA. The predictors were firm size, receivable turnover ratio, interest cover ratio, receivable turnover in days, price-to-book, current ratio, asset turnover ratio, leverage ratio, quick ratio, price-to-earnings, inventory turnover ratio, cost of sales ratio, and EBIT margin. Sixteen companies were identified, and the sample size was 640 observations. The variables found to influence ROE were quick ratio, leverage ratio, receivable turnover ratio, inventory turnover ratio, firm size, and cost of sales ratio. In contrast, ROA was influenced by the receivables' turnover ratio, cost of sales ratio, quick ratio, and price-to-book ratio.

Tuvadaratragool (2023) breaks down ROA into Net Profit Margin and Assets Turnover. To find determinants of ROE, they used ROA, Net Profit Margin, and Total Assets as independent variables. The listed companies on the Thai Stock Exchange for the period 2015 to 2019 were used to collect secondary data, with two sample sizes of 104 and 93. The combination of Total Assets and Net Profit Margin outperformed ROA in predicting ROE.

All the research above used a continuous dependent variable, ROE. Most of them were analyzed using Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), which requires many model assumptions to yield valid and reliable results. These assumptions are often not met; hence, in this study, we seek to use a binary dependent variable for ROE.

2.2 Machine Learning Methods

Yaswanth & Riyazuddin (2020) implemented seven ML techniques — Decision Tree (DT), LR, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Neural Networks, KNN, NB, and RF — to predict heart disease. The research used health care data from the University of California, Irvine ML repository, with a sample size of 303: 139 were positive and 164 were negative. The highest classification accuracy was achieved by Artificial Neural Networks (92.30%), while RF, LR, KNN, and NB achieved 85.71%, 81.71%, 80.21%, and 57.14%, respectively.

Balaraman (2020) used Google Colab to compare LR, KNN, SVM, RF, DT, and NB for breast cancer classification. The dataset was obtained from Wisconsin public records and comprises 569 cases (212 benign and 357 malignant). The number of features used, sourced from biopsy images, was ten (10), consisting of symmetry fractal, concave points, compactness, area, texture, radius, perimeter, smoothness, concavity, and dimension. The top classifier was logistic regression, with an accuracy of 98.5%. Meanwhile, KNN, RF, and NB had classification accuracies of 96.97%, 94.99%, and 93.47%, respectively.

To compare ML techniques in the classification of breast cancer, Alshammari & Mezher (2020) used thirteen machine learning techniques, which are Bayes Net K2 search, Bayes Net Tab search, Lazy-KStar, Bayes TAN search, NB, LR, Lazy-IBK, Rules Zero R, Trees Decision stump, Lazy LWY, Trees J48, RF, and Trees Random trees. The dataset was analyzed using Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) software with a sample size of 699 and 10 independent variables. Lazy-IBK and K Nearest Neighbor achieved the highest classification with an accuracy of 98.2%, while RF, NB, LR, and NB achieved 96.4%, 96.4%, and 92.8%, respectively. In breast cancer classification, Balaraman (2020) found that LR outperformed other ML techniques, while Alshammari & Mezher (2020) found that Random Forest outperformed them. This suggests that more research using different datasets is needed. It is also unclear which ML method is best for classification. In this research, we aim to extend the comparison of the four ML models to the Stock Exchange Market.

3. Methodology

3.1 The Dataset and Research Variables

The data was sourced from the Integrated Real-time Equity System (IRESS) website. IRESS contains a database of financial ratios for companies listed on the JSE from 1970. The dataset was collected using simple random sampling, selecting all companies listed on the JSE for the year 2019. The number of predictors before checking for multicollinearity among predictors was ten (10). One predictor was removed due to multicollinearity. The sample comprised 323 companies: 236 with positive ROE and 87 with negative ROE. To address the issue of the imbalanced dataset, the following methods were used:

- Firstly, the 2019 original imbalance dataset (dataset 1) was analysed using metrics such as precision, recall, ROC-AUC score, and F1 score, which are known to cope with imbalanced datasets. We also included accuracy to see how it would be affected by the imbalanced dataset.
- Secondly, the 2019 dataset was balanced using observations from previous years (dataset 2) while ensuring independence of observations. The observations to balance the dataset were selected from companies listed between 2000 and 2018. For each selected company, we selected one observation without missing values. The resulting sample size was 1074.
- Thirdly, SMOTE (synthetic minority oversampling technique) was utilized to correct the issue of an imbalanced dataset. In SMOTE, new data points are generated specifically for the minority class, while the majority class remains unchanged (Satpathy, 2024). Using SMOTE, 87 new observations were generated for the minority class. The resulting sample comprised 410 companies: 174 with negative ROE and 236 with positive ROE.
- Lastly, the ROSE (Random oversampling examples). ROSE is an oversampling technique that uses bootstrap-based methods and assists in binary classification of an imbalanced dataset. Using ROSE oversampling, 149 new observations were generated for the minority class, yielding a final sample size of 472. The dataset was now balanced with 236 companies with positive ROE and 236 with negative ROE.

In this study, the binary ROE is used as the dependent variable. In contrast, the metric independent variables include Quick Ratio (QR), Debt to Assets ratio (DTA), Earning yield (EY), Price per earning (PPE), Interest cover (IC), Net profit margin (NPM), Debt to equity ratio (DTE), Asset per capital employed (APCE), and earning per share (EPS). For validation purposes, the data were partitioned into 60% for training and 40% for validation.

3.2 Statistical models

The four statistical models used are Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB), and Random Forests (RF). A brief description of each of them follows.

3.2.1 Logistic Regression (LR)

The model for logistic regression is known as the Logit and is given by

$$\log\left(\frac{\pi_i}{1 - \pi_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \dots + \beta_p X_{pi} \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, n$$

where π_i is the probability of success and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p$ are parameters to be estimated and $X = X_1, \dots, X_p$ are metric independent variables.

The following model assumptions should be observed:

- Binay outcomes for the dependent variable.

- Observations from duplicated measurements or those that came from matched data.
- The absence of multicollinearity.
- The sample size requirements (augmented using oversampling methods).

Model fit in LR uses Deviance, Likelihood ratio test, Hosmer-Lemeshow, Classification Table, and the two Pseudo R^2 . The Wald statistic is an appropriate test for determining the suitability of including each predictor variable in the model (Healy, 2006; Franklin & Emmanuel, 2014). Predictors were included in the LR model if the Wald p-value was < 0.05 .

3.2.2 Random Forest (RF)

In random forest, for the n^{th} tree, a randomly selected vector θ_n is constructed, which is entirely free from $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n-1}$, previous random vectors, but equally distributed. The training dataset and a random vector θ_n are utilized in the growing of the tree. The resultant classifier becomes $h(x; \theta_n)$, where X stands for input vector. The most frequent class is voted after most of the trees have been generated, and the whole procedure is called Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001).

In RF, the two most used measures of variable importance are accuracy-based importance (also known as mean decrease accuracy) and Gini-based importance (also known as mean decrease impurity). The Gini-based importance was used for variable selection. The Gini-based importance method uses the Gini impurity to select a predictor for splitting a node. A predictor with a higher Gini importance was considered more important for predicting ROE.

3.2.3 Naive Bayes (NB)

A set of classification algorithms constructed using Bayes' theorem is called Naive Bayes. It uses the assumptions of feature independence and conditional independence to estimate the class of Y given a set of features. It is used to predict the values of $Y \in (0,1)$ given a new instance, $X = (X_1, \dots, X_n)$ and it uses the training dataset to estimate the values of $P(Y = y)$ and $P(X_i | Y = y)$. We write Naive Bayes Classifier as

$$\hat{y} = \arg \max_{y \in (0,1)} \left(\frac{P(Y = y) \prod_{i=1}^p P(X_i / Y = y)}{\sum_{j=1}^1 P(Y = j) \prod_{i=1}^p P(X_i / Y = j)} \right).$$

Naive Bayes in SPSS uses forward selection for variable selection. Independent variables were entered into the model based on average log-likelihood, with predictors having the smallest average log-likelihood first. The best subset of predictors selected was the one that produced the highest classification accuracy.

3.2.4 K-Nearest Neighbor

K-NN is defined by the arrangement of the dataset, $D = \{(X_1 Y_1), (X_2 Y_2), \dots, (X_n Y_n)\}$, in increasing order of magnitude for the purpose of accommodating the Euclidean distance. The ordered data set becomes $D = \{(X_{(1)} Y_{(1)}), (X_{(2)} Y_{(2)}), \dots, (X_{(n)} Y_{(n)})\}$ and according to Devroye et al. (1996), the K-NN is defined as

$$h_n(X) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sum_{i=1}^k w_i(Y_{(1)}(X)) = 0 < \sum_{i=1}^k w_i(Y_{(i)}(X)) = 1 \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases}$$

where the letter n represents the sample size and X the test instance. $Y_{(i)}$ is the same as $Y_{(i)}(X)$ the corresponding coordinate of $X_{(i)}$ in the i^{th} nearest neighbour of X . w_i 's are the weights of KNN

used to weight the dataset. When selecting variables, KNN uses forward selection. At each step, a variable that minimises the error rate is included in the model. It uses a variable importance chart or a predictor selection log to display the relative importance of each selected predictor. The predictor selection log is used to identify the important features.

3.3 Classification Table

The model's prediction accuracy can be measured using a classification table (Peng & So, 2002; Park, 2013). Hence, to compare the four machine learning techniques, metrics calculated from the classification table were used.

Table 1: Classification Table

Predicted	Actual Class	
	Positive	Negative
Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
Negative	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

In Table 1, TP refers to observations classified as positive, and TN to those classified as negative. FN refers to observations classified as negative, while FP stands for observations classified as positive but are negative (Bhandari, 2023). Using the classification table, the values of sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy were calculated for Logistic Regression, K-nearest neighbour, Naive Bayes, and Random Forest.

4. Data Analysis

We present the model assumptions' tests, followed by the comparisons of the four ML techniques (LR, KNN, NB, and RF) using an imbalanced dataset, SMOTE, ROSE, and a balanced dataset. We note that ML methods — RF, KNN, and NB — do not require many model assumptions, except that observations are independent. LR assumes an additional assumption of lack of multicollinearity. The dependent variable was originally metric, allowing VIF and tolerance to be calculated. Tables 4.1(a) and 4.1(b) show the tolerance and VIF for dataset 1 and dataset 2, after removing the current ratio (CR) variable.

Table 2(a) Tolerance and VIF without CR using dataset 1

Coefficients
Collinearity Statistics

Model	Tolerance	VIF
APCE	.565	1.770
DTA	.839	1.193
DTE	.515	1.941
EPS	.913	1.096
EY	.809	1.236
IC	.901	1.110
NPM	.852	1.174
PPE	.894	1.119
QR	.923	1.083

Dependent Variable: ROE

Table 2(b) Tolerance and VIF without CR using dataset 2

Coefficients
Collinearity Statistics

Model	Tolerance	VIF
APCE	.735	1.360
DTA	.758	1.319
DTE	.664	1.507
EPS	.917	1.091
EY	.844	1.185
IC	.826	1.210
NPM	.763	1.311
PPE	.996	1.035
QR	.861	1.161

Dependent Variable: ROE

From Table 2, all VIFs are below 5, and tolerances are below 1, indicating no multicollinearity.

4.1 Model comparison using dataset 1

The four statistical models were compared using the following evaluation metrics: Sensitivity, Specificity, Precision, F1 Score, Area under the ROC curve (AUC), and Accuracy. According to Singh (2023), AUC is better suited to an imbalanced dataset, while Accuracy is better suited to a balanced dataset. Table 3 shows the average performance of the four ML models. (The colours blue and red represent the best- and worst-performing models, respectively).

Table 3: Average Model Performance (training and test) with all predictors

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	94.2	79.5	67.2	96.6
Specificity	99.2	98.3	96.8	98.8
Precision	97.6	94.5	87.2	96.6
F ₁ Score	95.8	86.3	75.6	96.6
Accuracy	97.7	93.2	89.0	98.2
AUC	96.9	86.2	87.1	99.4

From Table 3, the worst-performing model was KNN, while the worst AUC was from Naive Bayes. The best-performing models were LR and RF, with the highest specificity and precision of 99.2% and 97.6%, respectively. RF dominated Sensitivity (Recall), F1 Score, Accuracy, and AUC, with values of 96.6%, 96.6%, 98.2%, and 99.4%, respectively.

4.2 Model Comparison for dataset 1 using the ROC curve

In Figure 1, the ROC curve for RF was more to the top left region of the graph than for LR, NB, and KNN. The AUC for the RF model also exceeded that of any other model. The RF graph was followed by the LR model, which also covered a larger area in the ROC curve. The NB model covered less area in the ROC curve, indicating it was the least performing model when using an imbalanced dataset. The KNN was the least-performing model across all evaluation metrics, except for AUC.

Figure 1: ROC Curve using dataset 1

4.3 Data Analysis using dataset 2

Variable selection, using all statistical models, was conducted first because of the larger sample size. All statistical models selected NPM, IC, EY, EPS, and PPE as the best predictors of ROE. RF was the only statistical model to validate the selected predictor using the training and test datasets. The results are shown in Tables 4 and 5, and Figures 2 and 3.

Table 4: Variables in the equation for LR using dataset 2

		Variable in the Equation		
		B	Wald	Sig
Step 5	EPS	.001	4.867	.027
	EY	.016	4.545	.033
	IC	.011	3.263	.071
	NPM	.166	55.596	<.001
	PPE	.006	3.044	.081
	Constant	-.047	.118	.731

Table 1: Variable Selection in NB using dataset 2

Subset Summary		
Subset	Predictor Added	Average Log-Likelihood
0	(initial subset) *	
1	NPM	-.503
2	EY	-.436
3	IC	-.391
4	EPS	-.360
5	PPE	-.335

*The initial Subset is empty

Figure 2: Predictor selection error Log for KNN using the training dataset

Figure 3: Variable Selection for RF using dataset 2

4.3.1 Model comparison using dataset 2

The model's parameters must be considered when selecting the best ML model for a given dataset (Ghosh, 2023). Before variable selection, there were nine predictors; after selection, five were identified as the best predictors of ROE. We compared the four statistical models both before and after variable selection.

Table 6: Average model performance (training and test) with all predictors

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	92.5	79.1	84.3	99.1
Specificity	98.2	95.7	90.9	98.4
Precision	98.1	94.8	90.3	98.4
F ₁ Score	95.2	86.2	87.2	98.8
Accuracy	95.4	87.3	87.6	98.8

From Table 6 with all predictors, NB was the worst performing model in terms of sensitivity, F1 Score, and Accuracy, while KNN performed poorly in terms of specificity and precision. LR was the second-best model. RF was the best-performing model, with sensitivities, specificities, precisions, F1 scores, and Accuracies of 99.1%, 98.4%, 94.4%, 98.8%, and 98.8%, respectively.

Table 7: Average model performance (Training and Test) with five predictors

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	91.9	82.0	91.0	99.3
Specificity	98.2	93.1	94.4	98.6
Precision	98.1	92.7	94.2	98.6
F ₁ Score	94.9	86.7	92.6	98.9
Accuracy	95.0	87.4	92.7	98.9

From Table 7, NB was the worst-performing model, with sensitivities, specificities, precisions, F1 scores, and Accuracies of 82%, 93.1%, 92.7%, 86.7%, and 87.4%, respectively. KNN with five predictors or after variable selection improved significantly. LR remained the second-best model and did not improve after variable selection. RF was the best-performing model, with sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1-score, and Accuracy of 99.3%, 98.6%, 98.6%, 98.9%, and 98.9%, respectively.

4.4 Model Comparison using the SMOTE dataset

Tables 8 and 9 show the results for the SMOTE dataset, before and after variable selection. Improvements were observed, especially in average specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy, with values of 99.6%, 99.6%, 98.4%, and 98.7%, respectively for LR. The performance of NB also improved after SMOTE oversampling, producing average sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy of 85%, 97.3%, 96%, 90.1%, and 92.1%, respectively. The KNN model was the worst-performing model before and after SMOTE oversampling. After variable selection, KNN outperforms NB on important metrics, including sensitivity, F1 Score, and Accuracy, with values of 90.6%, 91.2%, and 92.6%, respectively. RF performed better than other methods in terms of model performance before and after variable selection, but it produced the best model when using SMOTE oversampling without variable selection.

Table 8: Model comparison *without* feature selection using the SMOTE dataset

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	97.6	85.0	89.5	99.2
Specificity	99.1	97.3	87.0	100
Precision	98.8	96.0	83.0	100
F ₁ Score	98.1	90.1	86.0	99.6
Accuracy	98.5	92.1	87.8	99.7

Table 9: Model comparison with feature selection using SMOTE dataset

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	97.2	80.5	90.6	99.2
Specificity	99.6	98.9	94.2	99.6
Precision	99.6	98.3	91.9	99.6
F ₁ Score	98.4	88.5	91.2	99.4
Accuracy	98.7	91.2	92.6	99.5

4.5 Data Analysis using ROSE dataset

For the ROSE dataset, the average sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy for KNN without variable selection were 95.0%, 89.0%, 89.8%, 92.3% and 92.0% respectively, while after variable selection, it was 96.4%, 93.3%, 93.5%, 94.9% and 94.9% respectively. When comparing NB before and after variable selection, we noticed that NB with all predictors outperformed NB with variable selection. It was observed that LR after variable selection performed worse than LR before variable selection. The best model was produced by RF without feature selection, with average sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1 score, and accuracy of 100%, 99.1%, 99.2%, 96.6% and 96.6% respectively. Tables 10 and 11 show these results.

Table 10: Model comparison *without* feature selection using the ROSE dataset

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	100	86.5	95.0	100
Specificity	97.9	97.9	89.0	99.1
Precision	98.2	97.6	89.8	99.2
F ₁ Score	99.1	91.7	92.3	99.6
Accuracy	99.0	92.3	92.0	99.6

Table 11: Model comparison with feature selection using ROSE dataset

	Logistic Regression	Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
Sensitivity	97.1	85.7	96.4	100
Specificity	98.8	97.7	93.3	98.4
Precision	98.7	97.6	93.5	98.6
F ₁ Score	97.9	91.2	94.9	99.3
Accuracy	97.9	91.8	94.9	99.3

4.6 Variable selection using shrinkage methods

We determine how shrinkage methods perform in terms of feature selection. The three shrinkage methods used were Lasso, Elastic Net, and Ridge Regression. The results are shown in Table 12 and Figures 4, 5, and 6.

Table 4.12: Lasso, Elastic Net, and Ridge Regression (Training dataset 2)

	Logistic Regression	<i>p</i> -values	Lasso Regression	Elastic Net Regression	Ridge Regression
Intercept	0.17840	0.649	-0.86010	-1.22162	-1.60618
APCE	-0.00789	0.964	0.00000	0.01630	0.00165
DTA	-0.27335	0.538	0.00000	-0.06427	-0.08721
DTE	-0.04230	0.438	-0.09931	-0.17304	-0.15317
EPS	0.00126	0.033	0.47755	0.53806	0.48336
EY	0.01497	0.045	0.59205	0.66780	0.56697
IC	0.01134	0.063	0.46125	0.62333	0.53401
NPM	0.16406	0.001	5.05918	6.89091	9.08569
PPE	0.00592	0.070	0.21534	0.26058	0.24271
QR	0.00744	0.916	0.00000	0.03034	0.03298

Using the test dataset, it was found that the best predictors of ROE were NPM, EY, IC, APCE, and PPE. It was concluded that Logistic Regression, Lasso, Elastic Net, and Ridge regression were unable to fully validate their predictors using the training and test datasets. In the following sections, we will be looking at KNN, Naive Bayes, and Random Forest feature selection methods to see how they perform.

Figure 4: Variable selection using Lasso Regression and dataset 2

Examining Figure 4 and Table 12, it is evident that NPM was the last predictor to reach zero, followed by EY, EPS, IC, PPE, and DTE, while APCE, DTA, and QR were eliminated from the regression model because their coefficients were zero. According to Lasso, the best predictors of ROE were NPM, EY, EPS, IC, PPE, and DTE. However, we noticed in Table 4.12 that the coefficient for DTE was insignificant at -0.0994. This was supported by Logistic regression in Table 4.12, where the p -value for DTE was insignificant at 0.438. Hence, it was concluded that DTE must be removed from the regression model. The final predictors of ROE were NPM, EY, EPS, IC, and PPE.

Figure 5: Variable selection using Elastic Net Regression and dataset 2

Figure 6: Variable selection using Ridge Regression and dataset 2

In Figures 5 and 6 and Table 12, we observed that NPM, EY, IC, EPS, PPE, and DTE took time to reach zero. It was the confirmation of results found when Lasso Regression was used. The coefficients for NPM, EY, IC, EPS, PPE, and DTE when Elastic Net Regression was used were 6.8909, 0.6678, 0.6233, 0.5381, 0.2606, and -0.1730, respectively, while for Ridge Regression were 9.086, 0.5670, 0.5340, 0.4834, 0.2427, and -0.1532, respectively.

5. Discussion of Results

In this study, the four statistical models identified NPM, IC, EPS, EY, and PPE as the best predictors of ROE, with positive slopes of 0.166, 0.011, 0.001, 0.016, and 0.006, respectively. This means that a one-unit increase in NPM will increase ROE by 16.6%. Samiloglu et al. (2017) found that EPS and PPE were the best predictors of ROE when using a dataset collected from the Istanbul Stock Exchange for the period 2006 to 2016. Tuvadaratragool (2023) used a dataset collected from the Thai Stock Exchange and showed that NPM was the best predictor of ROE. In this research, NPM was a highly significant predictor identified by the four statistical models. This study also confirms findings by Abraham et al. (2017), who found that EY was a predictor of ROE. The results of this study are also supported by the DuPont formula, which shows that NPM and IC were among the drivers of ROE.

It was also found that APCE, DTE, DTA, and QR were not significant drivers of ROE. Similar results were reported by Aniyah et al. (2020), who found that QR and DTE were not significant in predicting ROE. Gharaibeh & Khaled (2020) also excluded DTA and DTE as predictors of ROE.

In dataset 2, we found that RF with feature selection outperformed RF without it. This was expected since model performance typically improves with variable selection. RF had the best model performance, followed by LR, KNN, and NB. The results confirm the findings of Yaswanth & Riyazuddin (2020), who found that RF outperformed LR, KNN, and NB.

For dataset 1, before oversampling, LR was affected by an imbalanced dataset since its specificity and sensitivity differ by $(99.2-94.2) = 5\%$. NB and KNN were also affected by the imbalanced dataset. RF achieved the highest classification with sensitivity and specificity of 96.6% and 98.8%

respectively and was not affected by an imbalanced dataset. Hamal & Senvar (2021) found that RF, LR, KNN, and NB were all affected by an imbalanced dataset. It is suspected that the difference in results was due to the dataset, as its minority class was more imbalanced at 18.83% compared to ours at 26.93%. Singh (2023) stated that AUC is suitable for an imbalanced dataset than Accuracy. In this study, for models affected by an imbalanced dataset (KNN, NB, and LR), and using F1-score as a benchmark, we noticed that the F1-score was closer to AUC than to Accuracy.

From dataset 1 with SMOTE oversampling, RF without feature selection outperformed RF with feature selection. It was a surprise because this contradicts the results we found in dataset 2, where RF with feature selection outperformed RF without feature selection. NB was one of the models that did not improve after feature selection. Similar results were reported by Hamal & Senvar (2021) using SMOTE oversampling and financial ratios to detect financial accounting fraud. They also discovered that RF without feature selection outperformed RF with feature selection. We noticed the signs of over-fitting in the SMOTE dataset. A sign of over-fitting is evident when an ML model improves performance by adding more predictors. Overfitting normally occurs when predictors are highly correlated with one another. According to Alkhaldeh, Albalkhi, and Naswhan (2023), SMOTE generates new instances that are similar to the minority class, leading to overfitting.

In dataset 1 with ROSE oversampling, RF without feature selection outperformed RF with feature selection, as observed with SMOTE oversampling. Over-fitting was also noticed with the ROSE dataset. The other two classifiers that could not improve their performances after feature selection, especially in terms of sensitivity, F1 score, and accuracy, were LR and NB. Hamal & Senvar (2021) found similar results when using SMOTE and financial ratios; none of their ML classifiers improved after feature selection in their dataset.

The model that highly benefited from feature selection in dataset 2 was KNN. Its sensitivity improved from 84.3% to 91%, the most significant improvement among all classifiers. It also improved tremendously from SMOTE and ROSE oversampling. LaViale (2023) confirms our results. They stated that feature selection in KNN reduces the dataset's dimensionality. It also reduces the number of variables used in KNN distance calculations, thereby lowering the algorithm's complexity. They further stated that calculating distances between samples can affect the KNN algorithm when dealing with an imbalanced dataset and can also degrade performance.

6. Conclusion

Negative ROE can repel current and potential investors from a company. It was also important to find the best statistical model for accurately predicting ROE and identify its best predictors. Many studies in the literature used ROE as a continuous dependent variable. To avoid the stringent model assumptions of MLR, we identified determinants of ROE using a binary dependent variable and four ML classifiers (LR, KNN, NB, and RF). Four datasets were used, and models were constructed and compared using model evaluation metrics, namely, sensitivity, specificity, precision, F₁ score, and accuracy. The selection of important predictors was performed using LR, KNN, RF, and NB feature selection methods.

In dataset 1, only the RF was not affected by the imbalance. This study confirmed that the F1-score and AUC are appropriate metrics for evaluating models on imbalanced data.

Using dataset 2, the four statistical models identified NPM, IC, EY, EPS, and PPE as the best predictors of ROE. RF was the only statistical model to validate the five selected predictors using the test dataset. For the SMOTE and ROSE datasets, only RF was used for variable selection, which successfully selected the five predictors (NPM, IC, EPS, EY, and PPE), and they were validated on the training and test datasets. RF outperformed all other models across all datasets, and LR ranked second. KNN was the only statistical model to improve significantly after feature selection and oversampling across all datasets.

It is known that model performance improves with feature selection. We found out in this study that all models improved after feature selection when using dataset 2. However, the opposite occurred with the SMOTE and ROSE datasets; performance decreased after feature selection. Over-fitting by the SMOTE and ROSE datasets was suspected. After oversampling, it was not easy to choose

between the SMOTE and ROSE datasets because RF performed very well on both, with key metrics above 99%. In fact, the ROSE dataset with RF produced a model that was good at predicting negative ROE, with average values after feature selection of 100% sensitivity, 99.3% F1-score, and 99.3% accuracy. The SMOTE dataset with RF also produced a good model with high precision. Dataset 2 (balanced using observations from previous years) produced excellent results without overfitting.

6.1 Recommendations

Since NPM, IC, EPS, EY, and PPE were found to be the best predictors of ROE, this study recommends that investors look for JSE companies with high NPM, high IC, high EPS, high EY, and low PPE when making investment decisions. This study also confirmed that the F1-score and AUC are suitable metrics for imbalanced data. Hence, the use of F1-score, AUC, and other suitable metrics is recommended for imbalanced data. For oversampling methods, the study recommends the use of both oversampling methods (SMOTE and ROSE) with caution, since both methods were prone to over-fitting. In research with a larger sample size, under-sampling of the majority class is recommended over oversampling of the minority class. Dataset 2 produced excellent, reliable results with no signs of overfitting; hence, where possible, the use of the original dataset via further sampling is recommended.

RF not only dominated ROE prediction but also feature selection. Generally, RF is known to perform well at predicting the response variable. However, in this work, only RF was able to validate its selected predictors across all datasets (dataset 1, dataset 2, SMOTE, ROSE) using training and test datasets. Hence, this study recommends using RF for feature selection and ROE prediction in companies listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange.

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